

TOXICOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF MALACHITE GREEN ON TILAPIA (OREOCHROMIS MOSSAMBICUS)

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Abstract

Malachite green (MG) is prohibited in fish farming in Vietnam due to its toxicological and carcinogenic properties. However, it continues to be illegally used in some areas. This study investigated the accumulation and depuration of MG in three organs—gills, liver, and muscle—of *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Tilapia), which represent the major toxicant entry routes: respiratory, digestive, and dermal, respectively. Under controlled laboratory conditions, the concentrations of MG and its primary metabolite, the reduced and colorless leucomalachite green (LMG), were analyzed using liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry. The results showed that MG primarily accumulated in the gills, with the lowest accumulation observed in muscle tissue. These findings suggest that tilapia have the ability to eliminate toxicants from their bodies. The fish demonstrated gradual adaptation to environments containing MG, with enhanced detoxification via excretory pathways over time. Notably, fish exposed to low MG concentrations were better able to adapt and eliminate the toxicant compared to those exposed to high concentrations continuously, indicating that exposure level plays a crucial role in the efficiency of detoxification.

Keywords: Malachite green, toxicological effects, analytical methods, pollutants, food sciences, LC-MS.

1. Introduction

Malachite green (MG) has been widely used in the aquaculture industry since the 1930s as a fungicide and ectoparasiticide, particularly for treating fish eggs, fingerlings, and adult fish [Error! Reference source not found.]. It is readily absorbed into fish tissues during waterborne exposure and is rapidly metabolized to its reduced, colorless form—leucomalachite green (LMG) [2, 3]. Due to its toxicological and potentially carcinogenic properties, the use of MG in aquaculture has been banned in many countries, including the United States and the European Union. Nevertheless, its low cost, high efficacy against fungi, bacteria, and parasites, and easy accessibility have led to continued illegal use in some regions.

35 In recent decades, concerns regarding the presence of chemical contaminants in aquatic
36 environments have been increasing globally, particularly in countries with intensive agricultural
37 and aquaculture activities. Numerous studies have reported the widespread occurrence of
38 pesticide residues in vegetables [4], heavy metals in aquatic organisms [5], and various organic
39 micropollutants in surface and drinking water sources [6, 7]. Such contaminants not only pose
40 ecological risks but also affect food safety and public health [3, 8, 9, 10, 11]. Numerous
41 researchers have increasingly focused on chemical monitoring and toxicological risk assessments
42 in aquatic ecosystems, employing advanced techniques such as high-resolution mass
43 spectrometry [4, 11], multiresidue screening [6, 9, 10], and metabolomic approaches [5, 9, 12].
44 In this context, toxicological studies on MG serve as an essential component of broader
45 environmental surveillance and aquatic toxicology.

46 Residues of MG in aquaculture products have been frequently reported in the Rapid Alert System
47 for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifications of the European Commission. MG and LMG have also
48 been detected in farmed fish imported into the UK, primarily from Southeast Asia [13, 14, 15].
49 The misuse of MG not only causes contamination of aquatic environments but also poses serious
50 risks to human health [16, 17]. Numerous studies have been conducted on the analysis, tissue
51 distribution, accumulation, and elimination of MG and LMG in fish following waterborne
52 exposure. For example, Alderman and Clifton-Hadley [3] investigated the pharmacokinetics of
53 MG in rainbow trout exposed to a 1.6 mg/L bath for 40 minutes, examining the effect of
54 temperature on MG persistence, although LMG was not considered. Law (1994) studied the
55 metabolism of MG and LMG in fingerling trout exposed to 2 mg/L MG for 1 hour and found that
56 MG levels decreased over time while LMG levels peaked at 24 hours post-exposure and then
57 remained stable for seven days [18].

58 Meinertz et al. (1995) measured MG residues in eggs and fry exposed to repeated treatments (1
59 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and found a residue level of 0.271 $\mu\text{g/g}$ on day 31, with a half-life of 9.7 days [19].
60 Plakas et al. (1996) examined MG uptake, distribution, and metabolism in channel catfish
61 exposed to 0.8 mg/L MG for 1 hour, reporting half-lives of 4.7 hours in plasma and 2.8 to 10
62 days in muscle for MG and LMG, respectively [2]. More recently, Jiang et al. (2009) evaluated
63 MG accumulation in various tissues (muscle, gill, liver, kidney, blood, skin, and gonad) of three
64 freshwater fish species in China. After an acute 6 mg/L MG exposure for 20 minutes, gill tissues
65 exhibited the highest MG levels at 0 hours, followed by a rapid decline of both MG and LMG in
66 blood. However, residues in muscle remained above 0.002 $\mu\text{g/g}$ at 240 hours post-exposure, and
67 LMG persisted particularly in fat-rich tissues such as skin and gonads. Notably, the distribution
68 of LMG was more influenced by tissue fat content than by feeding behavior [20].

69 These findings provide a foundation for understanding the organ-specific dynamics of MG
70 absorption and elimination in fish. Building upon this knowledge, our study focuses on the
71 temporal accumulation and elimination of MG and LMG in *Oreochromis mossambicus* (tilapia),
72 a species known for its hardiness, adaptability, and widespread use in aquaculture in Vietnam.
73 Tilapia is also included in the U.S. Food and Drug Administration's standard method for the

74 quantification of MG and LMG residues in fish and shrimp (FDA Method 4363), making it a
75 relevant model organism for this investigation.

76 **2. Materials and methods**

77 **2.1. Chemicals and Reagents**

78 All solvents used were of LC-MS grade, and all other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade
79 unless otherwise specified. Malachite green (MG) and leucomalachite green (LMG) were
80 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). Standard stock solutions (1 mg/mL) of MG and LMG
81 were prepared in acetonitrile and stored at 4°C; they remained stable for at least one month.

82 Formic acid (99.5%), acetonitrile, methanol, and dichloromethane were obtained from J.T.
83 Baker. Certified alumina-based solid-phase extraction (SPE) cartridges (500 mg, 6 mL) were
84 obtained from Sep-Pak Waters (USA). Sodium chloride was purchased from Merck and pre-
85 heated at 700°C for 6 hours prior to use.

86 Ultrapure water was generated using a Milli-Q Gradient A10 purification system (USA). A 0.1 M
87 acetate buffer at pH 4.5 was prepared freshly before use. A 25% hydroxylamine hydrochloride
88 (HAH) solution was prepared by dissolving 25.0 g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in 100 mL of
89 ultrapure water. A 0.05 M p-toluenesulfonic acid (p-TSA) solution was prepared by dissolving
90 0.95 g of p-TSA in 100 mL of ultrapure water.

91 **2.2. Animal Experiments**

92 The experimental fish, *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Tilapia), were obtained from an aquaculture
93 pond with no prior history of malachite green (MG) treatment. MG residues in the fish were
94 analyzed before the experiment using 6 to 8 replicates, and no MG residues were detected. The
95 average body weight of the fish was approximately 100 ± 5 g. Fish were acclimated for 7 days in
96 aquariums containing dechlorinated tap water, equipped with aeration and filtration systems.
97 During acclimation, water was changed daily. The mean water quality parameters during the
98 experiment were as follows: dissolved oxygen ≥ 4 mg/L; pH 6.5–8.5; temperature 20–23°C; and
99 no detectable free chlorine.

100 **• Experiment 1: Constant MG concentration with daily water changes**

101 MG was dissolved in a 70-L aquarium containing 30 fish, achieving a concentration of 100 ppb.
102 The aquarium water was completely changed every 24 hours, and MG was re-added to maintain
103 the 100 ppb concentration throughout 10 consecutive experimental days. The aquarium was
104 continuously aerated and filtered. Fish samples were collected every 24 hours. Muscle, gill, and
105 liver tissues were excised and stored at -20°C for subsequent MG and leucomalachite green
106 (LMG) analysis. Three fish were sampled at each time point. Reported values represent the
107 average concentrations of MG and LMG in the three tissue types.

108 **• Experiment 2: Single MG exposure without water changes**

109 In this experiment, MG was added once at the start to reach a concentration of 1000 ppb in the
110 aquarium, which was maintained for 7 days without any water changes or further MG additions.
111 Fish sampling and tissue analysis were conducted as described in Experiment 1.

112 **2.3. Analytical Procedures**

113 *2.3.1. Sample Preparation*

114 Based on methods reported in references [3,4,5,9], we developed a sample extraction procedure
115 for malachite green (MG) and leucomalachite green (LMG) in fish tissues. Approximately $2 \pm$
116 0.05 g of tissue sample was weighed into 50 mL centrifuge tubes. To each tube, 0.5 mL of 25%
117 hydroxylamine hydrochloride (HAH), 0.5 mL of 0.05 M p-toluenesulfonic acid (p-TSA)
118 solution, and 1 mL of 0.1 M acetate buffer (pH 4.5) were added. The sample was homogenized at
119 1600 rpm for 3 minutes. Subsequently, 10 mL of acetonitrile was added, and homogenization
120 was repeated. The mixture was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes, and the supernatant was
121 collected. The homogenization and centrifugation steps with 10 mL acetonitrile were repeated
122 once more.

123 To the combined supernatant, 10 mL dichloromethane and 1.5 g sodium chloride were added.
124 The sample was vortex-mixed thoroughly and centrifuged. The organic phase was then
125 evaporated to dryness. The residue was reconstituted in 3 mL of formic acid/acetonitrile (2:98,
126 v/v) and passed through a preconditioned alumina SPE cartridge (6 mL acetonitrile). The eluate
127 was collected and evaporated to dryness again. Finally, the analyte fraction was dissolved in 1
128 mL acetonitrile and used for LC-MS analysis of MG and LMG.

129 *2.3.2. Liquid Chromatography Equipment and Conditions*

130 Qualitative and quantitative analyses of MG and LMG were performed using a Shimadzu LCMS
131 2010A single quadrupole mass spectrometer (Japan) equipped with an autosampler, a Surveyor
132 LC pump, a Surveyor PDA detector, and an ion trap mass analyzer with an atmospheric pressure
133 chemical ionization (APCI) source operated in positive ion mode (APCI+).

134 Separation was achieved on an Agilent ZORBAX SB-C18 column (2.1×150 mm, $3.5 \mu\text{m}$
135 particle size; Agilent Technologies, USA). The mobile phase consisted of solvent A (water with
136 0.05% formic acid) and solvent B (acetonitrile with 0.05% formic acid). The linear gradient
137 program was as follows: 0 min, 5% B; 0.5 min, 40% B; 3 min, 60% B; 4 min, 80% B; 6 min,
138 80% B; 10 min, 5% B; maintained until 20 min. The flow rate was set at 0.3 mL/min. Column
139 temperature was maintained at 35°C , and the injection volume was $5 \mu\text{L}$.

140 Mass spectrometry tuning was performed using MG and LMG ions at m/z 329 and 331,
141 respectively. Quantification was carried out in Selective Ion Monitoring (SIM) mode. The
142 ionization interface voltage was set at +5000 V, and the interface temperature was maintained at
143 250°C .

144 *2.3.3. Recovery Experiments*

145 To assess the accuracy of the analytical method, recovery experiments were performed in
146 triplicate by spiking homogenized muscle samples (2 ± 0.05 g) with a mixed MG and LMG
147 standard solution to achieve a final concentration of 100 ppb in the tissue. Recovery percentages
148 were calculated based on measured versus spiked amounts. The average recoveries (n=4) were
149 $62.3 \pm 0.7\%$ for MG and $91.5 \pm 0.5\%$ for LMG.

150 3. Results and Discussions

151 3.1. Experiment 1: Constant MG Concentration with Daily Water Changes

152 The results (Fig. 1A) showed that the gills accumulated leucomalachite green (LMG) at levels
153 approximately 2.23 times higher than malachite green (MG). Peak accumulation of MG was
154 observed on day 3 (423 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), while LMG reached its maximum on day 4 (1893 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$).
155 However, LMG levels began to decline after day 4, whereas MG levels also initially decreased
156 but showed a slight increase from day 6 onwards. Overall, the total concentrations of MG and
157 LMG in the gills tended to decrease after day 6. This trend may reflect the physiological
158 regulation in fish, such as reduced uptake or enhanced excretion of toxicants.

159 The gill, as a major respiratory organ, functions primarily in gas exchange rather than metabolic
160 transformation. It acts as a natural barrier or filter but does not play a significant role in the
161 conversion of MG to LMG. Therefore, LMG observed in the gill likely results from direct
162 environmental exposure or systemic circulation, rather than in situ metabolism.

163

(C)

164
 165 **Fig 1. The evolutions of MG and LMG content in gill (A), muscle (B) and liver (C) in Experiment 1**
 166 In this experiment, MG was added daily to maintain its concentration in water. Despite this, MG
 167 levels in muscle tissue remained very low during the first four days (18, 19, 5, and 3 µg/kg,
 168 respectively) and became undetectable from day 5 onwards (Fig. 1B). This suggests that MG
 169 does not easily penetrate fish muscle through direct environmental exposure, and its
 170 accumulation in muscle may primarily occur via systemic absorption through the digestive tract
 171 and liver metabolism. The decreasing LMG levels in muscle over time could indicate adaptation
 172 of fish to long-term MG exposure, reducing further penetration or enhancing elimination.

173 The liver plays a central role in detoxification and metabolism. Figure 1C shows that the liver
 174 accumulated the highest total concentration of MG and LMG on day 3 (1951 µg/kg), followed
 175 by a gradual decrease. The proportion of LMG in total residues in the liver remained relatively
 176 constant (~60%) during the first three days and peaked at 76.4% on day 4. Although overall
 177 residue levels declined thereafter, the proportion of LMG relative to MG increased markedly,
 178 reaching 89% on day 6. This suggests that the liver not only accumulates LMG but also actively
 179 metabolizes MG into LMG.

180
 181 **Fig 2. Concentration of MG (A) and LMG (B) in 3 organs (gill, muscle and liver) in Experiment 1**
 182

183 Data from Figure 2 confirm that the highest total accumulation of MG and LMG occurred in the
 184 gills, approximately 2.5 times higher than the liver and 12 times higher than the muscle.
 185 Comparing liver and muscle, LMG concentrations in muscle were about half those in the liver,
 186 supporting the liver's critical role in both the formation and elimination of LMG. Among the
 187 three organs, the liver had the highest LMG concentrations, confirming its key metabolic
 188 function. In contrast, the gill acts more as a direct exposure site, serving as a passive barrier
 189 rather than an active metabolic organ.

190 **3.2. Experiment 2: Single MG Exposure Without Daily Water Changes**

191 In this experiment, MG was introduced only once at the beginning (day 0) at a concentration of
 192 1000 ppb. As shown in Fig. 3A, the liver accumulated LMG at concentrations approximately 2.5
 193 times higher than MG. Both MG and LMG levels peaked on day 4 and declined thereafter. The
 194 maximum MG concentration was observed on day 3 (7107 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), dropping to 1287 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ by
 195 day 7 — a 7-fold decrease. For LMG, concentrations decreased from a peak of 14,923 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ on
 196 day 3 to 5907 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ on day 7 — a 3-fold decrease.

197 Since MG was not replenished daily in this setup, its concentration in the water likely declined
 198 over time due to degradation, metabolism, or sorption. MG and LMG concentrations in muscle
 199 (Fig. 3B) showed an increasing trend over the first three days, followed by a decline — a trend
 200 similar to that observed in the gills. This suggests that systemic exposure and accumulation
 201 patterns were consistent across tissues during early exposure.

202 Figure 3C shows that in the liver, MG peaked on day 3 (3147 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), while LMG levels
 203 remained relatively stable during the first three days and then rose sharply to 3569 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ on day
 204 4. The more pronounced change in LMG concentration compared to MG reflects the liver's role
 205 as a metabolic organ, capable of transforming MG and eliminating toxicants.

Fig 3. The evolutions of MG and LMG content in gill (A), muscle (B) and liver (C) in *Experiment 2*

Fig 4. Concentration of MG (A) and LMG (B) in 3 organs (gill, muscle and liver) in *Experiment 2*. Figures 4A and 4B compare MG and LMG concentrations across all three tissues. Both MG and LMG levels were consistently lowest in muscle and highest in the gills. The MG accumulation trends were similar across all organs, indicating that fish may not have been able to adapt immediately to the high MG concentration (1000 ppb) during the early exposure phase. However, over time, fish appeared to adapt by enhancing elimination or transforming MG into other metabolites. In contrast, LMG accumulation trends varied by organ, particularly in the liver, likely due to its metabolic and excretory functions.

4. Discussions

The present study provides a detailed investigation of the accumulation dynamics and metabolic transformation of malachite green (MG) and its reduced form leucomalachite green (LMG) in tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) under two exposure scenarios. The findings revealed tissue-specific differences in accumulation patterns, with the gills exhibiting the highest concentrations of both MG and LMG, followed by the liver and then the muscle. This pattern highlights the significance of the gill as the primary site of entry for waterborne toxicants and as a passive filter rather than a metabolic organ.

226 In both experimental setups, the transformation of MG into LMG was clearly observed,
227 especially in the liver, confirming its role as the main site for biotransformation. The increasing
228 proportion of LMG over time suggests a consistent metabolic conversion and a possible
229 accumulation of the more persistent metabolite. Notably, the results indicated that repeated low-
230 dose exposure (Experiment 1) allowed fish to gradually adapt and enhance detoxification
231 mechanisms more effectively than a single high-dose exposure (Experiment 2). This observation
232 supports the idea that acclimation and metabolic regulation play critical roles in toxicant
233 management in aquatic organisms [21].

234 The differential accumulation among tissues also aligns with previous toxicological studies
235 showing that metabolic and excretory capabilities of fish are strongly organ-specific. For
236 instance, in a study on acrylamide contamination in daily food in urban Hanoi, the
237 bioaccumulation potential of certain substances was closely linked to metabolic activity in
238 different food matrices [22]. Similarly, bioaccumulation of pollutants in aquatic ecosystems has
239 been well documented in Vietnamese rivers, where organic micropollutants and trace metals
240 were found to concentrate in organisms depending on exposure duration and pathways [23, 24].

241 The gill, despite its high absorption rate, demonstrated a reduced metabolic capacity compared to
242 the liver, as reflected by the lower proportion of LMG. This is consistent with the role of the gill
243 as an interface organ for gas exchange and its limited involvement in enzymatic detoxification.
244 The muscle, representing the edible part of fish, showed the lowest accumulation, suggesting a
245 degree of protection afforded by hepatic and branchial metabolism. However, even trace levels in
246 muscle can be concerning for food safety, particularly in regions like the Red River Delta, where
247 aquaculture is often conducted near sources of industrial and agricultural runoff [25, 26].

248 Importantly, the adaptation capacity of fish observed in the repeated low-concentration exposure
249 experiment reflects broader biological resilience mechanisms, which are also observed in plants
250 exposed to contaminants in Vietnam. For example, studies on *Pteris vittata* and *Pityrogramma*
251 *calomelanos* showed differential arsenic uptake and tolerance depending on soil pH and
252 exposure conditions [27], which parallels the variable detoxification capacity in fish across
253 tissues and over time.

254 Furthermore, the findings have implications for environmental health in polluted areas of
255 Vietnam, where a wide array of natural and anthropogenic contaminants—including secondary
256 metabolites [28, 29, 30], emissions from livestock farming [25, 31], and ozone-inducing fuels
257 [32]—interact and potentially exacerbate toxicity. The ability of aquatic species to metabolize
258 and excrete such substances determines not only their survival but also the safety of aquaculture
259 products destined for human consumption.

260 As chemical and biological complexity in aquatic systems increases due to urbanization and
261 climate change, toxicological evaluations like this study are essential. They complement ongoing
262 research efforts on pollutant screening [23], chemical constituent characterization [28, 33], and
263 adaptation mechanisms in both aquatic and terrestrial organisms [21, 34, 35]. Collectively, such

264 studies contribute to a more holistic understanding of environmental risks and the development
265 of safer aquaculture practices.

266 5. Conclusions

267 This study provided an initial evaluation of malachite green (MG) and leucomalachite green
268 (LMG) accumulation in tilapia under controlled laboratory conditions. As one of the early
269 investigations on MG toxicity in this species, the findings contribute to a better understanding of
270 toxicokinetics and tissue distribution in aquatic organisms.

271 MG and LMG were found to accumulate in all three major exposure routes: through the gills
272 (respiratory), liver (digestive), and skin/muscle (dermal). Among these, the gills exhibited the
273 highest levels of accumulation, while muscle tissues showed the lowest concentrations. This
274 distribution suggests that gills serve as the primary entry point for MG, whereas the muscle may
275 reflect longer-term, systemic exposure or residual retention.

276 Physiological effects observed in exposed fish included softened muscle texture, faded
277 coloration, and the appearance of red spots in the gills, indicating potential tissue damage and
278 systemic stress caused by MG and LMG.

279 The results also highlight the adaptive capacity of tilapia to toxic exposure. Fish exposed to
280 lower, consistent concentrations of MG over time demonstrated improved detoxification and
281 elimination capabilities compared to those subjected to high, sustained concentrations. These
282 findings suggest that gradual, sublethal exposure may allow fish to activate physiological
283 defense mechanisms more effectively, leading to enhanced resilience against environmental
284 toxicants.

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